

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science

IMPLEMENTATION Phase

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02 | TYPE OF ACTION: HORIZON-CSA | GA n. 101079148

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

Lead author: Piotr Targowski

With contributions from: Magdalena Kowalska, Rémi Petitcol, Elodie Cazenave and Vania Virgili

ABSTRACT

This deliverable presents the work carried out within E-RIHS IP to support the establishment of new E-RIHS National Nodes and strengthen the existing ones.

It provides a comprehensive overview of the methodology employed to identify key challenges faced by both prospective and established Nodes in preparing to participate in the future E-RIHS ERIC. The results of a detailed National Nodes survey are then presented. They served as the basis for organising two targeted workshops: one focused on already established National Nodes (Krakow, June 2023) and another aimed at potential new European or international partners (online, May 2024).

The deliverable concludes with concise practical guidelines to address the most commonly encountered challenges and offer perspectives for the implementation and growth of E-RIHS National Nodes. This guidance aims at facilitating the integration of National Node into the distributed infrastructure and strengthen their role within the heritage science community.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project number	101079148	Acronym	E-RIHS IP
Full title	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Implementation Phase		
Project url	www.e-rihs.eu		
EU Project Officer	Tiziana della Ragione		

Deliverable	Number	D2.4	Title	Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node
Work Package	Number	2	Title	Governance and Structure of E-RIHS

Deliverable nature	Report		
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	30/09/2024		
Actual delivery date	19/12/2024		
Status	Final	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final	

Authors (Partner)	NCU		
Responsible Author	Name: Piotr Targowski	Partner: NCU	

Total number of pages	41
Keywords	Distributed infrastructure; National Node organisation.

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
23/08/2024	1	Piotr Targowski	Initial version
10/10/2024	2	Rémi Petitcol Elodie Cazenave	Addition of new chapters
17/10/2024	3	Piotr Targowski, Rémi Petitcol, Elodie Cazenave, Vania Virgili, Polonca Ropret	Creation of the implementation table
30/10/2024	4	Rémi Petitcol Elodie Cazenave	Editing
18/11/2024	5	Vania Virgili	Revised version based on E-RIHS IP partner feedback
18/12/2024	6	Piotr Targowski & Vania Virgili	Final editing

DISCLAIMER: This document reflects only the author(s)'s view and the Agency, and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. It reflects the state of advancement of the project work at the time of its delivery. As such, its content may be subject to further evolution and has not been endorsed or validated by the E-RIHS interim General Assembly.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	7
2. METHODOLOGY FOR ENGAGING WITH NATIONAL NODES AND COLLABORATION WITH OTHER TASKS	9
3. THE E-RIHS IP NATIONAL NODE SURVEY	11
3.1. OBJECTIVES	11
3.2. METHODOLOGY	11
3.3. RESULTS AND NEXT STEPS	16
4. THE WORKSHOPS FOR STRENGTHENING NATIONAL NODES AND ENLARGING E-RIHS PARTICIPATION	17
4.1. CONTEXT AND OBJECTIVES	17
4.2. SHARING EXPERIENCE WITH OTHER RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES	17
4.3. E-RIHS ENLARGEMENT WORKSHOP: EXTENDING COLLABORATIONS INSIDE AND OUTSIDE EUROPE	18
4.4. BILATERAL ACTIONS AND NEW OPPORTUNITIES	20
5. IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES	21
6. CONCLUSION: TOWARDS THE ERIC E-RIHS	24
REFERENCES	25
ANNEX I. RESULTS OF THE NATIONAL NODE SURVEY	26
ANNEX II. PROGRAMMES OF THE WORKSHOPS	27
ANNEX II-1. PROGRAMME OF 7 JUNE 2023	27
ANNEX II-2. PROGRAMME OF 17 MAY 2024, OPENING SESSION	28
ANNEX II-3. PROGRAMME OF 27 MAY 2024, CLOSING SESSION	29
ANNEX III. TEMPLATE OF NATIONAL CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT	30

LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1: Status of the National Nodes establishment 12

Table 2. Characteristics of the access 13

Figure 1: Governance structure of E-RIHS ERIC. 7

Figure 2: Chart representing the linkages between T2.2 and other tasks. 9

Figure 3: Structure of Nodes by countries. 12

Figure 4: Structure of the Nodes by the number of partners – collectively..... 13

Table 2: Characteristics of the access 13

Figure 5: Access procedures by type, together in 2022 and 2023. 14

Figure 6: Types of institutions with which users are usually associated. Approximate distribution. 14

Figure 7: Other activities performed by Nodes, by the number of nodes involved – 17 Nodes reported. 15

ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	EXPANSION
ARCHLAB	ARCHive LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together organized scientific information in largely unpublished datasets from archives of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
CNN	Committee of National Nodes of E-RIHS
DIGILAB	DIGital LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that provides remote access to heritage science data, supplemented with digital services and tools within a virtual research environment (under development)
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
E-RIHS PP	E-RIHS Preparatory Phase
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures
FIXLAB	FIXed LABoratory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together fixed research facilities and associated scientific experience of their staff that develop and maintain sophisticated state-of-the-art instrumentation for advanced diagnostics and archaeometry (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
GA	General Assembly of E-RIHS

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

HS	Heritage Science
HS Academy	E-RIHS training program in heritage science delivered through various formats, including doctoral summer schools, on-site training camps, webinars, lecture series, and specialized modules. The program is designed for both E-RIHS users and providers.
MOLAB	Mobile LABORatory: E-RIHS access platform that brings together European laboratories offering state-of-the-art mobile equipment and related competencies, for in-situ non-destructive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments and sites (https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/)
SLA	Service Level Agreement
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

The *European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science* (E-RIHS) is a distributed infrastructure based with a Central Hub that hosts the legal headquarters of the future *European Research Infrastructure Consortium* (ERIC), alongside a network of National Nodes that implement the activities at the national level. This governance structure is typical of distributed European Research Infrastructures and is similar to that of many other ERICs. The governance structure of E-RIHS is illustrated below:

Figure 1: Governance structure of E-RIHS ERIC.

The E-RIHS ERIC Statutes define National Nodes as “[...] *scientific communities of each Country involved with E-RIHS [constituting] the National Node, with its own National Coordinator*”. This definition remains broad by design, establishing two primary applicable obligations for National Nodes:

- Representing a national community involved in E-RIHS;
- To appoint a National Coordinator.

The Committee of National Nodes (currently an interim body) is composed of each National Coordinator, representing their Nodes. Its main role is to “*ensure consistency, coherence, and stability of the activities of the National Nodes*” and to “*oversee and monitor the implementation and coordination of E-RIHS ERIC policies in the network*” (E-RIHS ERIC Statutes, Art. 20).

National Nodes are autonomous entities that are not formally part of E-RIHS ERIC. They organize themselves based on their local situation, with ad hoc governance structures and internal rules. This

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

design choice was a conscious governance choice based on the experience of other ERICs. It aims to implement the subsidiarity principle within the structure as a good practice.

This principle states that *“issues should be dealt with at the most immediate or local level that is consistent with their resolution”*¹. As outlined in the E-RIHS Preparation Phase D2.4 on governance of central and national hubs, *“this means that the National Nodes deal with most issues directly involving the facilities and national matters, whereas European, strategic and crosscutting issues are dealt with at the European level”*².

This means that National Nodes are largely responsible for providing access to the E-RIHS platforms and training opportunities and are also a key element in the E-RIHS communication strategy. They are not directly bound by internal E-RIHS ERIC rules such as the rules of procedures (see D2.6), but their relationship with the ERIC is regulated by separate Service Level Agreements (SLA, see D2.1).

In collaboration with other tasks and work packages, Task 2.2 on supporting the establishment of E-RIHS National Nodes aims at:

- A better understanding of the practical requirements for National Nodes;
- Helping Nodes to create or strengthen their governance and operational structure based on a given national context;
- Provide the project with a comprehensive picture of the current situation of national nodes to guide the preparation of other deliverables and activities;
- Elaborate general guidelines and recommendations on National Node operations.

This deliverable describes the collective work carried out within Task 2.2 and WP2 over a period of more than two years, in close collaboration with the interim Committee of National Nodes (iCNN), the Enlargement Board (EB), and individuals working to establish an E-RIHS National Node in new countries. This work was closely linked to the political timeline of the creation of the ERIC, which should be established by the end of the year.

This document first describes the methodology used to engage with National Nodes, either directly or through collaboration with other tasks (Chapter 2), then focuses on the results of the T2.2 survey (Chapter 3) and the two National Nodes workshops (Chapter 4). Following this, it implements guidelines (Chapter 5) and concludes with perspectives towards the establishment of E-RIHS ERIC (Chapter 6).

¹ E-RIHS PP D2.4

² Ibid.

2. METHODOLOGY FOR ENGAGING WITH NATIONAL NODES AND COLLABORATION WITH OTHER TASKS

Engaging with National Nodes calls for different approaches and processes.

As a preliminary step, a survey was prepared to gather up-to-date information on the state of preparation of National Nodes (already established or in the process of being launched) for their participation in the E-RIHS ERIC.

The survey was prepared within T2.2 based on the decision of the Interim Committee of National Nodes made on the 12th of October 2022. The preparation of this survey was a collaborative process through several online meetings and also involved other Work Package leaders or participants, who were able to include questions that would also help with their tasks.

It was sent on 13th April 2023 to representatives of 25 countries through EUsurvey, and 17 countries responded – all where the national node was established or were at the final stage of the organization.

Based on the survey results, two workshops were organized:

1. One workshop on requirements, opportunities and best practices tailored for E-RIHS National Nodes where their current level of organization will be explored.
2. One workshop addressed to potential new E-RIHS members.

The content of these workshops, together with the choices of speakers were based on the most common challenges faced by National Nodes as identified in the survey for the first one or through exchanges within the Enlargement Board for the second one.

As a pivotal task between the National Nodes and the future ERIC, Task 2.2 on supporting the establishment of E-RIHS National Nodes worked in strong collaboration with other tasks and work packages. Its collaboration network is represented in the chart below.

Figure 2: Chart representing the linkages between T2.2 and other tasks.

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

As part of Work Package 2 on Governance and Structure of E-RIHS, the work on supporting National Nodes was carried out in close collaboration with T2.1, which is designing the contractual and regulatory relationship between the future ERIC and the Nodes, and T2.3, which is improving the Central Hub. As a key body of the ERIC, the Central Hub will provide executive assistance and processes to National Nodes.

The link with other Work Packages was also crucial, especially with the tasks related to risk management (T3.3) and quality system (T3.4) that heavily rely on good implementation by National Nodes, with the task on the enlargement strategy (T4.2) for the second workshop, with task T4.3 on the training, and T5.1 on the implementation of DIGILAB and T5.2 on the future E-RIHS Catalogue of Services.

Furthermore, to exchange good practices and share knowledge on a level of preparation for joining ERIC, all Nodes presented their status during dedicated meetings of the interim Committee of National Nodes. These meetings were extremely helpful in directly sharing good practices and solutions between members of the Committee.

Continuous participation of the iCNN was necessary to ensure an efficient and smooth process. This was reinforced by bilateral exchanges with specific National Nodes, either via email or dedicated meetings.

The E-RIHS Research Infrastructure Advisory Board (RIAB) was established to provide expert advice and guidance to the consortium throughout the different stages of the project. It was established on 11 October 2023 and is composed of two experts from distributed infrastructures: Ornela de Giacomo, deputy executive director of C-ERIC³, and Jennifer Edmond, associate professor at Trinity College Dublin and former director and president of DARIAH⁴. It provided direct advice on key topics that were passed on to National Nodes through various channels.

Another approach used by this task to identify good practices for distributed infrastructures and their national nodes was to consult already established infrastructures with a proven track record on the topic. These consultations were carried out through direct exchanges with executives and senior staff of several other European research infrastructures, including CESSDA⁵, CLARIN⁶, ELI⁷, EMSO⁸, EPOS⁹, Euro-Bioimaging¹⁰. Additional insights were gathered through engagement with structured forums such as the ERIC Forum¹¹ and the Italian ERIC Forum as well as participation in key conferences, including Roadmap 2026 InfoDay (Brussels, 8 Oct. 2024), Research Infrastructures in a Changing Global, Environmental and Socio-economical Context (Brussels, 4-5 Jun. 2024), Global Dimension and Sustainability of Research Infrastructures (Tenerife, 25-26 Sep. 2023).

³ C-ERIC (Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium), <https://www.c-eric.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

⁴ DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities), <https://www.dariah.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

⁵ CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives), <https://www.cessda.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

⁶ CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure), <https://www.clarin.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

⁷ ELI (Extreme Light Infrastructure), <https://eli-laser.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

⁸ EMSO (European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and Water Column Observatory), <https://www.emso.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

⁹ EPOS (European Plate Observing System), <https://www.epos-eu.org> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

¹⁰ Euro-Bioimaging ERIC, <https://www.eurobioimaging.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

¹¹ ERIC Forum, <https://www.eric-forum.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

3. THE E-RIHS IP NATIONAL NODE SURVEY

3.1. Objectives

The main objective of the survey was to capture a “snapshot” of the stage of preparation of National Nodes for participation in ERIC. As stated, knowledge about the level of advancement of Nodes is fragmented, covering only some parts of the full picture. Moreover, as it turned out, it comes from reporting at different times, so it does not reflect a synchronous picture of the level of preparation. In particular, it was difficult to determine which Nodes are delayed in relation to others.

3.2. Methodology

In order to obtain the fullest possible picture, an extensive survey was developed. The survey consists of 28 questions. To assist respondents and make the answers more unambiguous, a short glossary of terms used in the document is provided before the questions. It is divided into five sections:

Section 1: General Information

In this section, we ask whether a Node has been created, what institution runs it, how large it is, and what position the respondent holds in the Node.

Section 2: Structure of the National Node

This section concentrates on the legal status of the Node.

Section 3: Access

This section is dedicated to access to facilities provided by node participants. If so, we ask whether access is provided via a competitive process and whether the rules for access provision are formalised in a public document. Also, is there personnel formally dedicated to access management, how it is funded, and is it free for the user? Then, we would like to know some statistics related to accesses offered and completed.

Section 4: Budget.

This section concentrates on ways of financing the Node at present and in the future and on the accounting methodology.

Section 5: Future plans

In this section, we ask about an estimated level of participation in the Transnational Access (TNA) of ERIC, participation in DIGILAB, and data management. Finally, we ask for plans of joining E-RIHS ERIC. Detailed results of the survey are given in Annex 1. Only selected results and conclusions are presented here.

Table 1: Status of the National Nodes establishment

COUNTRY	MEMBER OF IGA?	NODE ESTABLISHED?	ACCESS TO ERIC - STEP2?	WHO RESPONDED
Belgium	YES	YES		National coordinator
Cyprus	NO	NO	YES	National coordinator to be
France	YES	YES	YES*	Host institution employee
Greece	YES	YES		National coordinator
Hungary	YES	YES	YES	National coordinator
Italy	YES	YES	YES	National coordinator
Malta	YES	YES	YES	National coordinator
Netherlands	YES	NO	YES	National coordinator
Poland	YES	YES	YES	National coordinator
Portugal	YES	YES		National coordinator
Romania	YES	YES	YES*	National coordinator
Slovenia	YES	YES	YES	Chair of the Management Board and national coordinator
Spain	YES	YES	YES	National coordinator
United Kingdom	YES	YES	YES*	National coordinator
Denmark	NO	YES		National coordinator
Norway	NO	NO		National coordinator to be
Sweden	NO	NO		National coordinator to be

*Participation confirmed after closing the survey.

Invitations have been sent also to the following countries: Austria, Brazil, Czech Republic, Germany, Israel, Mexico, US-East, US-West.

For the future functioning of the infrastructure, the composition of the nodes is essential:

Figure 3: Structure of Nodes by countries.

The diversity of the structure is well visible. However, when averaged over all members, the predominance of academic and research institutions and public museums is evident:

Figure 4: Structure of the Nodes by the number of partners – collectively.

Among functioning National Nodes, most (8) were established under legally binding agreements, whereas four of them were under a memorandum of understanding, three were under a consortium agreement, and one was functioning as a joint research unit. Four nodes were established under a non-binding agreement, and one is restricted to one institution. There are no nodes with legal personality.

Most of the Nodes offer access to their facilities. However, the rules and procedures are different among participating countries (see Table 2).

Table 2. Characteristics of the access

Country	Access provided in 2023?	Competitive access process?	Access rules public?	Dedicated access management personnel?	Dedicated access cost funding?	User access fee?
Belgium	NO					
Cyprus	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES
France	NO*					
Greece	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Hungary	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Italy	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO
Malta	NO*					
The Netherlands	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES
Poland	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
Portugal	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO
Romania	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
Slovenia	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO
Spain	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO
UK	NO*					
Denmark	NO*					
Norway	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	YES
Sweden	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO
Total YES	12	7	8	7	5	3

* Access is planned in the future.

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

Figure 5: Access procedures by type, together in 2022 and 2023.

Public sector: museums, libraries, NGOs and other public.

Figure 6: Types of institutions with which users are usually associated. Approximate distribution.

In addition to providing access, Nodes undertake other activities to support the heritage science and preservation community. These activities are not equally distributed over National Nodes, but globally, the most popular are the preparation and implementation of research projects and training.

Figure 7: Other activities performed by Nodes, by the number of nodes involved – 17 Nodes reported.

However, it is worthwhile to note that if some Nodes reported one or two kinds of activities, the maximum reported number is nine (all sorts of activities) and the median = 5.

The budget of nodes was the most diverse category. Most nodes report no funding at this stage, so they are waiting for the establishment of ERIC. In the case of Nodes founded (2022), the following sources were reported:

- Financial contributions from member/partner institutions
- European Structural Investment Funds
- National funding (from national funding agencies/ministries/analogous institutions and organisations)
- Regional funding (from regional funding agencies/analogous institutions and organisations)
- Access fees from public bodies/organisations
- Access fees from private organisations
- Private donations or grants (e.g. from foundations, charities)
- European Commission grants

Founding via EU projects (different than IPERION HS and E-RIHS IP) was reported by four Nodes (Italy, Slovenia, Portugal and Spain). The financing was targeted at:

- Joint Research Activities
- Training
- Research projects
- Public engagement
- Recommendations for policy-making or standardisation
- Networking and synergies with other European initiatives
- Other

The final part of the survey was dedicated to the Nodes' future plans. Among other things, the Nodes were asked about plans to provide access via the ERIHS ERIC Catalogue of Services. Most of the Nodes confirmed—the total number of services can be estimated to be 19 ARCHLAB offers, 136 FIXLAB offers, and 143 MOLAB ones. This leads to 300 procedures and ARCHLAB access sites, which imposes significant administration challenges.

Through this survey, the potential of prospective infrastructure members was assessed for the first time. However, it must be remembered that it is a “snapshot” of the status in early 2024 and the conditions are dynamic. Nevertheless, some conclusions can be driven:

- Nodes are composed chiefly of academic and research institutions
- access is provided mostly for public institutions: museums, libraries, etc. and research entities
- in addition to providing access, Nodes perform many other diverse activities
- for efficient management of E-RIHS ERIC, a precise reporting system must be introduced: there is no doubt that in some cases, questions were not articulated precisely enough, and some misunderstandings in answers occurred.
- as for the financing, the level is very uneven, and the European sources of funding are not used extensively enough
- it is expected that a huge number of procedures will be offered for access. It will need organisation precautions to be handled properly.

3.3. Results and Next Steps

The results of the survey were used to program further steps for the preparation of the infrastructure. Following the task description, two workshops were prepared in response to the needs revealed by the survey. One was dedicated to E-RIHS National Nodes (during the iCNN meeting in Krakow), and the other to potential new members (E-RIHS Enlargement Workshop – Extending Collaborations Inside and Outside Europe).

4. THE WORKSHOPS FOR STRENGTHENING NATIONAL NODES AND ENLARGING E-RIHS PARTICIPATION

4.1. Context and Objectives

E-RIHS IP strategy towards its National Nodes is mainly carried out in the framework of T2.2, however, T2.2 is supported in its endeavour of widening E-RIHS European and international collaborations by T4.2 Enlargement strategy and T6.3 Strengthening E-RIHS collaboration on the EU scene and beyond.

The organisation of workshops and other meeting opportunities by T2.2 actively contributed to (i) creating synergies within E-RIHS by reinforcing collaboration between National Nodes (ii) and widening the scope of E-RIHS collaborations further than its current reach.

Continued interaction with the iCNN was paramount for the success of these initiatives: to share good practices between existing National Nodes and to prepare for the integration of new Members through tailored service.

The perspective of the upcoming ERIC was an inciting background both for arbitrating on how the National Nodes shall interact with it, and/or nurturing interest among external institutions.

4.2. Sharing Experience with Other Research Infrastructures

4.2.1. WORKSHOP “STRENGTHENING NATIONAL NODES FOR E-RISH ERIC: CURRENT STATUS, BEST PRACTICES, AND RECOMMENDED ADJUSTMENTS”

On the occasion of E-RIHS IP first interim meeting in June 2023 in Krakow, Poland, a first hybrid workshop focusing on National Nodes was organised. The results and lessons from the E-RIHS National Node survey were presented and discussed with the E-RIHS broader community. Furthermore, the event gathered other ERICs such as C-ERIC and Euro-Biolmaging, which contributed to the common reflection by sharing insights and advice for future adjustments in the E-RIHS strategy towards National Nodes. With 48 participants from 10 member states in person, the workshop provided important outputs for T2.2, T4.2 and the iCNN. The full programme is available in Annex II-1.

4.2.2. RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ADVISORY BOARD MEETINGS

The E-RIHS Research Infrastructure Advisory Board (RIAB) was set up on 11 October 2023 to enable a structured exchange of good practices between distributed ERICs. It is composed of Ornella de Giacomo, deputy executive director of C-ERIC, and Jennifer Edmond, associate professor at Trinity College Dublin and former director and president of DARIAH. Their combined expertise covers both access to physical and digital services and the general management of an ERIC. Three meetings were carried out in October 2023, February 2024 and November 2024, where E-RIHS IP WP leaders exchanged freely on challenges and solutions for successfully managing a distributed ERIC. Some of the advice received is reflected in Chapter 5 of this deliverable.

4.3. E-RIHS Enlargement Workshop: Extending Collaborations Inside and Outside Europe

This event was addressed to prospective members of the infrastructure from and outside of the European Union – and therefore was organised in strong collaboration with T4.2 *E-RIHS Enlargement strategy* and with the support of T6.3 *Strengthening E-RIHS collaboration on the EU scene and beyond*. The workshop was composed of three parts and held online. Recordings of all sessions are available on the E-RIHS YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/c/ERIHSEU>), ensuring access to the shared information and reinforcing the long-term enlargement strategy.

The first and **opening session** was held on 17 May 2024 with the objective of introducing E-RIHS and presenting the long history of projects that prepared the infrastructure launch, its activities, its scientific vision, the development and improvement of the services offered, cutting-edge training opportunities, and different collaboration opportunities. The complete programme is available in Annex II-2.

Bilateral working sessions have been organised afterwards for interested partners. They have been arranged by geographical regions and scheduled on a one-to-one basis to allow more informal and direct exchanges with interested scientists and/or decision-makers in order to plan further collaboration activities. These four bilateral working sessions helped enlarge E-RIHS geographical outreach, inside and outside Europe, and were organised with Norway, Denmark, Austria, Brazil, Egypt, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and United Arab Emirates in the week between 20th and 24th of May 2024. Drawing from D4.4 *E-RIHS IP Enlargement Strategy*, the outputs of the bilateral working sessions are summarised as follows.

Working session with Norway and Denmark

Current status of E-RIHS in both countries was presented.

Further topics that were discussed:

- Integration of a new national node within E-RIHS ERIC, as a unique access point;
- Joint policy development on Heritage Science (e.g., ethical materials sampling procedures, joint development of standardised protocols, data storage and copyright property);
- Benefits that E-RIHS provides to academic and scientific institutions in terms of interdisciplinary research opportunities and advancements of science in general;
- Challenges of sustainability and environmental impact in the face of climate change.

Working session with Austria

Current status of E-RIHS in Austria was presented by the National Coordinator.

Further topics that were discussed:

- Legal requirements to join the ERIC as a Member;
- Elaboration of a National Node consortium agreement. A template was developed based on the experience of the French Node and discussed on this occasion and is available in Annex III of this deliverable;
- Strategy for integrating cultural heritage institutions within Nodes as partners or associated partners.

Working session with Brasil

Discussed topics:

- The situation of the ResInfraPlus EU-LAC project¹² and the possibilities of participation of Antecipa as a community targeted group;
- The preparation of the G20 Culture in Brazil and the opportunities to promote collaboration between Antecipa and E-RIHS at a political level;
- Antecipa's request for help to deal with the emergencies caused by the floods in Brazil;
- Digital interoperability and databases for heritage sciences and the role of E-RIHS' DIGILAB platform;
- The training activities, conferences and workshops planned by Antecipa and the possibility of involving E-RIHS colleagues;
- The Into Past BR project approved by the Ministry of Science and Technology of Brazil and the potential for bilateral collaboration with European institutions.

Working session with Egypt

Egyptian E-RIHS network was presented, and the discussion was oriented in the expectations of Egypt from E-RIHS and its contribution E-RIHS. Further exploration of collaboration with Egypt is underway, facilitated by the efforts of the Slovenian Node. An international conference, *Connecting Heritage Science to the Heritage of Science*, is scheduled to take place April 6th to 9th, 2025, at the Bibliotheca Alexandrina in Alexandria. The event will feature a dedicated session on E-RIHS.

Working session with the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

The heritage science activities of Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) were introduced. It was agreed the E-RIHS would need to submit an official letter to the Heritage Commission CEO - Ministry of Culture, KSA to initiate collaboration. This letter, sent in December 2024, outlined the key points for potential joint collaboration.

Working session with United Arab Emirates

Representatives from Abu Dhabi Emirate (UAE), including representative of the Heritage & Art Sector at the Ministry of Culture, participated alongside colleagues from the scientific community, such as the Louvre Abu Dhabi and various universities.

- They express strong interest in collaboration with E-RIHS;
- Possible topics for collaboration (e.g., pilot projects in modern heritage, training);
- Inspired by Egyptian example;
- Interested to sign a Memorandum of Understanding with E-RIHS.

Further planning of next bilateral meetings.

The **closing session** was held on 27 May 2024 and was the opportunity to summarise the exchanges and to outline the key outputs of the workshops. The complete programme is available in Annex II-3.

Next steps to further engage with interested countries have been drawn out: a MoU has been signed with Brazil, one is being negotiated with Egypt, and additional meetings are foreseen with United Arab Emirates.

In total, 12 attendees from 5 (Denmark, Norway, Brasil, United Arab Emirates, Egypt) took part in the workshop.

¹² <https://resinfra-eulac.eu> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

4.4 Bilateral Actions and New Opportunities

These bilateral actions, together with the sustained work of the rest of the project and the iCNN, have strengthened the relationship with key partners and opened new opportunities for collaboration.

Success story: E-RIHS Austria

The Austrian heritage science community, which was not involved in the European projects that led to E-RIHS (including E-RIHS IP), has communicated a very clear wish to join E-RIHS ERIC. This community is now structured in a National Node, and the participation of Austria as a Member of the ERIC is under active discussion.

Success story: Collaboration with Egypt and the Middle East

The successful collaboration of E-RIHS with the *Egyptian National Network of Science Centres and Museums* will continue next year with a dedicated international conference on “Connecting Heritage Science to the Heritage of Science” to be held at Bibliotheca Alexandrina, Alexandria, Egypt (6–9 April 2025). The program includes a presentation of E-RIHS and further discussion on collaboration between Egyptian institutions and E-RIHS is planned. In order to expand collaboration of E-RIHS to a broader Arab region, a dedicated session on International Collaboration on Heritage Science is included in the program, where interested stakeholders from Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Oman, Morocco and Jordan are also planned to join.

Success story: Participation in the CLASMAC 2024 meeting in Mexico

Very few Latin American heritage scientists participated in the enlargement workshop. Given the well-known vitality of heritage science in the region and the historical ties between Mexican partners and the E-RIHS community through the IPERION HS and EU-CELAC ResInfra project, it was decided to increase the outreach to Latin America outside of Brazil. The *Congreso Latinoamericano de Arqueometría, Arte y Conservación del Patrimonio Cultural* conference, CLASMAC 2024¹³, was held in Mexico from 9th to 13th September 2024 in Mexico City and gathered scientists and cultural heritage professionals from several Latin American countries. E-RIHS was presented in a keynote speech by Kilian Laclavetine (C2RMF, E-RIHS France) called “E-RIHS - una comunidad europea de las ciencias del patrimonio – oportunidad para la comunidad latinoamericana” on 13th September, followed by open discussion. This conference has raised the awareness of E-RIHS in Latin America and will pave the way for future exchanges with Mexican or other regional institutions.

Success story: MoU with Antecipa

In October 2024, E-RIHS and Antecipa formalised their collaboration with the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). The MoU highlights shared objectives, including joint research projects, training programmes, and strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change on cultural heritage. Furthermore, following the severe floods in Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil, in April-May 2024, E-RIHS issued a call to action to mobilise expertise across its community. The response focused on key interventions such as drying, decontaminating, and restoring damaged collections, as well as capacity building and the provision of essential equipment and materials. This collaboration not only addressed the immediate challenges but also laid the groundwork for long-term initiatives in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and climate justice, showcasing the effectiveness of global collaboration in heritage science.

¹³ <https://www.clasmac2024.unam.mx> [accessed 18 Dec. 2024]

5. IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES

Although the political and scientific contexts are different in each participating or prospective country, the results of the National Node survey, the bilateral exchanges and the workshop all point to common challenges related to implementing a successful E-RIHS National Nodes.

These challenges can be clustered into several categories:

- **Financial challenges.** These challenges can be linked to cash or in-kind contributions to either the ERIC or the National Node itself.
- **Governance challenges.** These challenges can be further divided into national issues (i.e., related to the relationship between Node partners) or European issues (i.e., related to the relationship with ERIC or one of its bodies in particular).
- **Scientific and organisational challenges.** These challenges are related to the implementation of E-RIHS ERIC or national activities.

Although some solutions and guidelines can be context-dependent and may need adjustments, we recommend the following approach to implement a successful National Node:

CATEGORY	CHALLENGE	RECOMMENDATION	REFERENCE DOCUMENTS/LINK
Financial	How to report financially to the ERIC? (ERIC-related and local activities)	Identify and implement national accounting obligations and implement E-RIHS accounting guidelines. Make use of the dashboard to track access units. Use unit costs as much as possible. In-kind contributions should be accounted for using the E-RIHS Accounting guidelines that are based on the current European Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.	D2.3 <i>E-RIHS Accounting Guidelines for Service Provision Costing</i> , and Horizon Europe supporting documents
Financial	How to report activities to the ERIC?	Continuous reporting is done by email through the Central Hub and CNN meetings. Yearly reports to the ERIC will follow a dedicated template. National activities that are related to the ERIC can be presented in an internal National Node report.	Internal communication plan* and National Node reporting template*
Financial	How to get national funding?	Each National Node is funded independently and must explore national or other funding opportunities. E-RIHS ERIC will provide	

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

CATEGORY	CHALLENGE	RECOMMENDATION	REFERENCE DOCUMENTS/LINK
		letters of endorsement upon request.	
Governance	How to sign the SLA as a Node?	Include a provision on delegation of signature in the national consortium agreement.	National Consortium Template (in D2.3) and D2.2 <i>E-RIHS SLA Template</i>
Governance	How to establish a national governance structure?	Identify the national obligations to ERIC members in the statutes and other ERIC documents and create a national structure based on these obligations.	National Consortium Template (in D2.3)
Governance	Should we include cultural heritage institutions in the node?	The formal inclusion of such partners is a national decision to make. In order to be active at the ERIC level, cultural heritage institutions must be able to provide a service (access, training, communication, etc.) to the European community with a high level of scientific quality. Signing cooperation agreements between national nodes and such institutions is also an option to be considered.	National Consortium Template (in D2.3), D3.5 <i>E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan</i> , D4.5 <i>Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy</i> , D5.6 <i>E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy</i>
Scientific and organisational	How to coordinate local non-access related services?	Inform the committee of national nodes and the central hub of these activities through a dedicated system. Implement the Training Strategy guidelines. Appoint national representatives in the HS Academy Editorial Board. Participate in the National Communication Officers Group	D4.5 <i>Revised Training Strategy</i> , D6.2 <i>Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy of E-RIHS ERIC</i>
Scientific and Organisational	How to coordinate outreach activities nationally and internationally?	Coordination is done through continuous communication at different level: CNN, communication officers or HS Academy. In all cases the Central Hub can act as an information relay. Establish internal communication mechanisms within the National Node	Internal communication plan*, D6.2 <i>Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy of E-RIHS ERIC</i>

CATEGORY	CHALLENGE	RECOMMENDATION	REFERENCE DOCUMENTS/LINK
		(shared online workspace, communication groups, etc.)	
Scientific and organisational	How to include partners that did not participate in IPERION HS or new partners?	Set a clear admission procedure for new national partners. Implement the E-RIHS Quality plan. Discuss the inclusion of their offer to the catalogue of services or HS Academy through the CNN. Negotiate their inclusion through update of the SLA.	<i>D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan, D4.5 Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy, D5.6 E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy</i>
Scientific and organisational	Should we organise "national access"?	E-RIHS ERIC delivers a single entry point to access platforms. However, National Nodes can organise matchmaking services between their partners and local communities for short, routine or exploratory projects.	<i>D5.6 E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy</i>
Scientific and organisational	How to engage with civil society and broader communities?	Participate or promote events, etc. to increase public visibility. Explore citizen science options. Connect with NGOs.	
Scientific and organisational	How can we participate in European projects through E-RIHS?	E-RIHS ERIC will communicate internally on open European calls for projects and provide matchmaking services between its members. Interested partners can communicate their intention to participate in a project to the Central Hub.	
Scientific and organisational	How to participate in DIGILAB?	The DIGILAB platform is currently being implemented. This implementation will set up both centralised and distributed services. National Nodes will also be able to provide access to expertise as service.	<i>D5.1 DIGILAB Implementation Plan</i>

* To be produced by the ERIC in 2025.

6. CONCLUSION: TOWARDS THE ERIC E-RIHS

The distributed nature of E-RIHS is a strength. E-RIHS National Nodes are driving the integration of local scientific and cultural heritage communities into the infrastructure and are able to more accurately address their needs through a common language and national activities. They also provide agile structures to better implement various activities, including delivering access to the E-RIHS platforms. The representation of these national communities of stakeholders through the Committee of National Node (CNN) will provide the ERIC valuable insights on the needs and current trends of Heritage Science and enable the infrastructure to better implement its mission and vision.

However, having an additional layer with the overall structure of E-RIHS also generates governance, financial, organisational and sometimes scientific challenges. National Nodes are autonomous structures that are freely constituted by national partners. As such, each National Node is different and develops in a unique, evolving national context but must implement common European E-RIHS policies and objectives. This common framework and shared past European integration projects provide a similar incentive structure and consequently similar challenges.

These challenges were jointly identified through various means and confirmed by direct exchanges with national coordinators and their teams. The proposed agile solutions for facing these challenges were also designed by and for the National Nodes. At the time of writing of this document, when the creation of the ERIC is due very soon, several National Nodes success stories can be observed, and interesting developments are unfolding in new potential partner countries. This collective endeavour will continue in the first year of the ERIC operations, when National Nodes will start implementing E-RIHS ERIC activities.

REFERENCES

- Andrews, M., & Grau-Bove, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D4.5 Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13148658>
- Benassi, L., Manconi, S., Chaban, A., Carmona Quiroga, P. M., Castillejo, M., Silvia, I., Andrews, M., Fremout, W., Padfield, J., & STRIOVA, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D6.2 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategy of E-RIHS ERIC*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10985840>
- De Luca, L., & Guillem, A. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D5.1 DIGILAB Implementation Plan*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13622848>
- Doherty, B., Andrews, M., & Virgili, V. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14314559>
- E-RIHS. (2024). *E-RIHS Statutes (V10.04.2 2024.07.29)*, including Annex II Financial (v. 0.5.3 2024.09.05)
- Etgens, V., Laclavetine, K., & Petitcol, R. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D5.6 E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14178720>
- Pallot-Frossard, I., & Petitcol, R. (2020). *E-RIHS PP D2.4 Governance of central and national hubs*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14532390>
- Petitcol, R., & Cazenave, E. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.3 E-RIHS Accounting Guidelines for Service Provision Costing*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14438974>
- Petitcol, R., Cazenave, E., & Graber-Soudry, O. (2023). *E-RIHS IP D2.1 Draft of E-RIHS SLA Template (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8407328>
- Petitcol, R., Cazenave, E., & Graber-Soudry, O. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.2 E-RIHS SLA Template*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14242512>
- Ropret, P., Strlič, M., Virgili, V., & Lea, L. (2024). *D4.4 E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13483635>
- Weterings, M., & Van't Hof, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.6 Updated E-RIHS Rules of Procedure*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14184748>

ANNEX I.

RESULTS OF THE NATIONAL NODE SURVEY

The survey and the complete report on the survey results is accessible at:

Targowski, P., Kowalska, M., Doherty, B., Petitcol, R., Ropret, P., Sotiropoulou, S., Strlič, M., van t'Hof, J., & Virgili, V. (2024). *E-RIHS IP National Node Info Survey*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14185231>.

ANNEX II.

PROGRAMMES OF THE WORKSHOPS

Recordings of all sessions are available on the E-RIHS YouTube channel:
<https://www.youtube.com/c/ERIHSEU>.

Annex II-1. Programme of 7 June 2023

E-RIHS
NATIONAL NODE
PUBLIC WORKSHOP
Hybrid event

IMPLEMENTATION Phase

Wednesday, 7 June 2023

- 9:00-9:30
Registration and welcome coffee
- 9:30-9:35
Introductory speech
Vania Virgili (CNR) E-RIHS IP coordinator
- 9:35-9:50
Results and Lessons from the National Node survey
Piotr Targowski (NCU)
- 9:50-10:30
The Multi-level Governance of E-RIHS: next steps
Moderator: Rémi Petitcol (FSP)
- The contractual relationship between the ERIC and National Nodes**
Ohad Graber-Soudry (X-Officio)
remote participation
- Contributing to the ERIC as a National Node: services and in-kind contributions**
Ornela De Giacomo (CERIC)
- 10:30-11:00
Open discussion
- 11:00-11:30
Coffee break
- 11:30-11:45
Operating a Distributed Research Infrastructure
Antje Keppler (Euro-Bioluming)
remote participation

- 11:45-12:15
Building a Sustainable E-RIHS through Smart Planning and Funding
Moderator: Matija Strlič (UL)
- Business Model for Research Infrastructures**
Ilaria Nardello (ERAMARIS)
remote participation
- **The ARCHE Mapping Exercise: Opportunities for Boosting E-RIHS National Nodes**
Alexandre Caussé (FSP), ARCHE Coordinator
- 12:15-12:45
The Added Value of Research Infrastructure Ecosystem
Moderator: Vania Virgili (CNR)
- The Contribution of Research Infrastructures to EOOSC**
Bob Jones (EOOSC, Board of Directors)
remote participation
- The European Research Area: Research Infrastructures, Access, and Future Directions**
René Martins (EC DG RTD-ERIC)
- 12:45-13:00
Closing remarks
Polona Ropret (ZVKDS), chair of the E-RIHS (interim) Committee of National Nodes

E-RIHS
EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

IPERION HS

E-RIHS IP is a project funded by the European Union HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02 under GA 101079148

IPERION HS is a project funded by the European Union, H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1, under GA 871034

Annex II-2. Programme of 17 May 2024, opening session

E-RIHS
Enlargement
Workshop
Opening session

IMPLEMENTATION Phase

Friday 17 May, 2024 | h 3:00pm - 4:30pm CEST

15:00 Introduction
Piotr Targowski, Polish National Node of E-RIHS

15:05 Insight into E-RIHS: Mission, vision and activities
Vania Virgili, interim Director General of E-RIHS ERIC-to-be
Polonca Ropret, Chair of the Interim National Node Committee of E-RIHS ERIC-to-be

15:15 Questions (Q&A)

15:25 20 years of access: History and highlights
Brenda Doherty, Italian National Node of E-RIHS

15:40 Questions (Q&A)

15:50 Development and improvement of E-RIHS services
Piotr Targowski, Polish National Node of E-RIHS

16:00 HS Academy
Matija Strlič, Slovenian National Node of E-RIHS

16:10 E-RIHS collaboration opportunities and requirements
Rémi Petitcol, French National Node of E-RIHS
Paula Maria Carmona Quiroga, Spanish National Node of E-RIHS

16:20 Questions (Q&A)

16:30 Presentation of next sessions and closing remarks

■ **BILATERAL WORKING SESSIONS**
For interested partners will be arranged by geographical region and scheduled one-on-one to discuss specific situations and answer questions.

■ **CLOSING SESSION. Monday, 27 May, 2024 | h 3pm CEST**
To summarise the inputs and outline next steps

 E-RIHS
EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

 European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
Implementation Phase (E-RIHS IP) has received funding
from the European Union HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02
under the agreement No.101079148

Annex II-3. Programme of 27 May 2024, closing session

E-RIHS Enlargement Workshop

Closing session

IMPLEMENTATION Phase

Monday 27 May, 2024 | h 15:00 - 16:30 CEST

15:00 Introduction and Chairing
Piotr Targowski, Polish National Node of E-RIHS

15:15 Follow-Up from Bilateral Meetings with Brazil, Denmark and Norway, Egypt, Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates
Polonca Ropret, Chair of the Interim National Node Committee of E-RIHS
Vania Virgili, interim Director General of E-RIHS

15:30 Questions (Q&A)

15:45 Follow-Up from Bilateral Meetings with Austria: Agreement for operating a National Node
Rémi Petitcol, French National Node of E-RIHS

16:00 Questions (Q&A)

16:15 Closing Remarks
Vania Virgili, interim Director General of E-RIHS

Online event

PARTECIPATE HERE

E-RIHS
EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
Implementation Phase (E-RIHS IP) has received funding
from the European Union HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02
under the agreement No.101079148

ANNEX III.

TEMPLATE OF NATIONAL CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT

This template is an adapted version of the French National Node agreement. It must be translated and adapted to the local context. This Annex is published as a guide for National Nodes. It is not mandatory for National Nodes to follow this structure, although it is important that formal agreements are signed between all parties of a National Node.

PARTNERSHIP AGREEMENT

Whereas:

- The Parties possess scientific equipment and resources operated by research teams recognised internationally in the various disciplines that constitute heritage science;
- Heritage science contributes to the in-depth knowledge of heritage and to the improvement of its preservation and transmission;
- Interdisciplinary cooperation fosters synergy between stakeholders and strengthens the European and international position of (COUNTRY) in the knowledge and conservation of heritage materials;

The Parties agree to the present partnership agreement (hereinafter referred to as "the Agreement").

CHAPTER 1: Scope of the Infrastructure

Article 1 — Purpose of the Agreement

The purpose of this Agreement is to define the conditions under which the Parties will collaborate within the framework of the infrastructure entitled:

"European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science – (COUNTRY)"

Hereinafter referred to as "E-RIHS (COUNTRY)", which involves laboratories or platforms, constituted as access providers to specific scientific equipment, resources, or expertise (hereinafter referred to as "access providers"), with the consent of their supervisory bodies. The list of these access providers is specified in Annex 1.

The Parties acknowledge that E-RIHS (COUNTRY) is the national node of the distributed European infrastructure "European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science" (E-RIHS, hereinafter referred to as "E-RIHS Europe"), and that they are thereby participating in the French contribution to E-RIHS Europe.

Article 2 — Missions of E-RIHS (COUNTRY)

The missions of E-RIHS (COUNTRY), in line with those of E-RIHS Europe, are defined around four main areas: access to various platforms, training, transdisciplinary research common to all heritage actors, and digital:

- Provide access to cutting-edge scientific resources and associated expertise to academic researchers, researchers from cultural and creative industries, heritage professionals, and national and European industries;
- Stimulate research and innovation in all disciplines that constitute heritage science, such as the humanities and social sciences, experimental sciences, and digital sciences;
- Promote best practices and innovative methods that meet the needs of researchers and heritage professionals in material characterization, identification of degradation mechanisms, evaluation, and development of conservation treatments, or any other matters related to in-depth heritage knowledge;
- Provide initial and continuing training that reflects the diversity of themes, challenges, and professions that constitute heritage sciences;
- Support its members in the digital transition with a view towards open, collaborative science, oriented towards Europe and the international stage.

Article 3 — Activities of E-RIHS (COUNTRY)

In order to carry out the missions of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) as outlined in Article 1.2 above, the Parties shall implement the following activities within the framework of the Agreement (hereinafter referred to as "Activities"):

- In terms of access provision, implement the selected projects within the framework of E-RIHS Europe for projects involving access providers linked to the Agreement, and launch additional project calls reserved for E-RIHS (COUNTRY) members and their partners. The project calls from E-RIHS Europe are launched under the responsibility of E-RIHS Europe and are reviewed by an independent evaluation committee.
- In terms of training, active participation in E-RIHS Europe's doctoral schools, summer schools, and other training activities under its "Heritage Science Academy" program, as well as the establishment of additional activities primarily reserved for members of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) or where applicable, its national partners.
- In terms of methodological research activities based on the needs of the heritage science community, organising consultations and drafting best practice guides in collaboration with user representatives and various heritage professions.
- In terms of digital, participation in the E-RIHS DIGILAB platform and the implementation of its national component, ensuring coherence among the various initiatives of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) members.

CHAPTER 2: Members, Access Providers, and Associated Partners of E-RIHS (COUNTRY)

Article 4 — Members of E-RIHS (COUNTRY)

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

The Parties to the Agreement are considered members of E-RIHS (COUNTRY). The Parties participate in E-RIHS Europe through E-RIHS (COUNTRY), which is the national node of E-RIHS Europe. The members of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) are the authorities responsible for the access providers listed in Annex 1.

Article 5 — Membership of E-RIHS (COUNTRY)

Recognizing the importance of interdisciplinarity and integration of the heritage science community, the Parties agree on the following membership rules for institutions wishing to join as members:

- Entities wishing to join E-RIHS (COUNTRY) as members must submit a written request to the Chair of the Steering Committee. This request must describe the candidate entity's potential contribution to the infrastructure, identify the access providers within its scope, and provide a quantified assessment of the access to be made available to E-RIHS (COUNTRY).
- The membership request is evaluated by the Steering Committee and approved by a two-thirds majority of the votes cast by the members. The results are communicated to the candidate entity by the Chair of the Steering Committee.
- The entity's membership takes effect on the date of signature of an amendment to the Agreement by the incoming institution and the lead institution, acting on behalf of the other Parties.

Article 6 — Membership of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) as an Access Provider

6.1 For laboratories or research units wishing to become an access provider of E-RIHS (COUNTRY):

- Candidate laboratories must have at least one parent authority that is a member of E-RIHS (COUNTRY). In the case of a laboratory with multiple parent authorities, this justification must be accompanied by an agreement from the other parent authorities.
- Candidate laboratories must submit their application to the Chair of the Steering Committee through the representative of one of their supervisory bodies. The application must describe the scientific contribution offered to the infrastructure, as well as the costs and modalities of the access proposed.
- The application is evaluated by the Steering Committee after consultation with the Scientific Council. The results are communicated to the candidate laboratory by the Chair of the Steering Committee.
- With the agreement of the responsible parent authority and the lead institution, the new access provider is listed in Annex I of the Agreement, and its commitments are described in Annex II.

6.2 The Chair of the General Assembly of Access Providers maintains the list of access providers in Annex I up to date.

Article 7 — Associated Partners

7.1 Acknowledging the great diversity of institutional actors involved in heritage sciences and the administrative heterogeneity that results from it, the Parties may, on a case-by-case basis and through specific agreements, decide to associate other entities based within the national territory with E-RIHS (COUNTRY) (hereinafter referred to as "Associated Partners"). These agreements shall

outline the rights and obligations of the Associated Partners and their participation in the various Activities. Such agreements will be signed by the National Coordinator following a decision by the Steering Committee.

7.2 A proposal for an Associated Partner may be initiated by one of the Parties or by the National Coordinator. It shall be assessed and approved by the Steering Committee.

Article 8 — Conditions for Withdrawal and Termination of Member or Access Provider Status

8.1 Unless mutually agreed by the Parties, the cessation of a Party's participation shall not affect any of the ongoing Activities, including Activities linked to E-RIHS (COUNTRY)'s multi-year commitments to E-RIHS Europe.

8.2 Subject to the above condition, any Party may terminate its participation in this Agreement by simple notification, with six (6) months' notice, addressed to the Chair of the Steering Committee.

8.3 Any Access Provider may terminate its participation via its parent authorities by simple notification no later than 30 September of the current year, addressed both to the Chair of the Steering Committee and the President of the General Assembly of Access Providers. Its participation shall cease on 31 December of the same year. However, the relevant Access Provider commits to honour any access requests validated by the evaluation committees of E-RIHS Europe or E-RIHS (COUNTRY) before the submission of its withdrawal notice.

8.4 In the event of a serious breach of obligations by a Party, the Steering Committee may decide to withdraw its member status or the access provider status of a laboratory under its administrative supervision.

The Party in question shall have a period of six (6) months from the date of formal notice to either justify its actions or rectify the breach. This formal notice is sent to the Party's representative by the Chair of the Steering Committee following a decision taken under Article 10.2 (p). After this period, the Steering Committee shall convene and deliberate on whether to withdraw the status of member or access provider, based on the responses provided by the entity concerned.

CHAPTER 3: Governance of E-RIHS (COUNTRY)

Article 9 — Governance Structure

The E-RIHS (COUNTRY) infrastructure is governed by:

- A Steering Committee,
- A National Coordinator,
- A Scientific Council,
- A General Assembly of Access Providers.

Article 10 — Steering Committee

10.1 The Steering Committee:

- a) Appoints or dismisses the National Coordinator and, if applicable, the Deputy Coordinator;

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

- b) Appoints the members and Chair of the Scientific Council, upon the proposal of the National Coordinator;
- c) Proposes to the Parties the strategy to be implemented to enhance the Activities, particularly in terms of European commitments;
- d) Approves the Activities to be implemented each year, based on the National Coordinator's proposal, and recommends the necessary corresponding resources;
- e) Adopts the annual operating budget for the Activities and allocates resources between the proposed Activities, sending it for validation to the management board of the lead institution;
- f) Approves the annual report on Activities prepared by the National Coordinator;
- g) Assesses the use of access by E-RIHS (COUNTRY) users and provides guidance to the National Coordinator on negotiating and renewing the "Service Level Agreement" between E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and E-RIHS Europe;
- h) Validates the association of third-party organisations with Activities as an Associated Partner;
- i) Approves the admission of a new access provider to E-RIHS (COUNTRY) after consulting the Scientific Council;
- j) Ratifies the internal rules detailing the organisational and operational procedures of governance bodies and Activities, and specifying the terms of access to services provided by access providers;
- k) Makes any recommendations to the Parties regarding potential amendments to the Agreement;
- l) Acts as a mediator to resolve any disputes between the Parties concerning the execution of the Agreement and, in the event of a serious breach by a Party, validates the withdrawal of member status as provided for in Article 8.4.

10.2 Composition

10.2.1 The Steering Committee is composed of one representative per Party. As of the date of the signing of the Agreement, the representatives are listed in Annex I.

Each representative has one (1) vote.

The Parties may replace their respective representatives, provided that notification is given to the Chair of the Steering Committee.

Each representative of a Party may appoint a third party to replace them at a Steering Committee meeting, provided prior notification is given to the other representatives. Any representative may also grant a proxy to another member of the Steering Committee, with the understanding that no member may hold more than one (1) proxy.

10.2.2 The National Coordinator attends Steering Committee meetings in an advisory capacity. The National Coordinator may be assisted by members of the Parties' staff, subject to the Steering Committee's approval.

If necessary, the Chair of the Steering Committee may, either on their own initiative or at the suggestion of members, invite to the meetings:

- (i) The Director-General of E-RIHS Europe or the Chair of the E-RIHS national nodes committee,
- (ii) Any expert deemed relevant to the agenda items, whether they are staff members or affiliated with the Parties or an external expert,
- (iii) Any representative of the Associated Partners.

10.2.3 The aforementioned persons attend Steering Committee meetings in an advisory capacity and must respect the confidentiality of any information exchanged at these meetings by signing a confidentiality agreement if they are not members of the Parties' staff. This confidentiality agreement is established between the individual and the lead institution, which is authorised by the other Parties to act in this regard.

10.3 Functioning

10.3.1 The Steering Committee elects a Chair from among its members by a simple majority for a term of two (2) years, renewable once. To encourage rotation of the Chair position, no Party may chair the committee more than twice consecutively.

10.3.2 The Steering Committee shall meet at least once (1) per year and as needed, at the initiative of its Chair or at the request of any other member. Meetings are convened by the Chair, with an agenda circulated at least fifteen (15) days in advance, along with a draft agenda prepared by the Chair in consultation with the National Coordinator, considering any points proposed by members.

10.3.3 The Steering Committee may only validly deliberate if a representative of each Party is present or represented. If a quorum is not met, the Chair may decide to postpone the meeting to within fifteen (15) working days. In such cases, the quorum is reduced to two-thirds of the members present or represented.

10.3.4 The decisions of the Steering Committee referred to in Article 10.1 shall be made by a two-thirds majority of the members present or represented; decisions referred to in Article 10.1 (n) shall also require validation by the management board of the lead institution.

10.3.5 In urgent cases, the Chair may decide to use an adapted consultation procedure. In this case, members are consulted individually and outside of a meeting, and their opinions and votes must be submitted in writing. The Chair shall report the results of this written consultation at the next Steering Committee meeting.

10.3.6 Minutes of the Steering Committee meetings shall be drafted by the National Coordinator. The minutes shall be sent to each member of the Steering Committee within fifteen (15) days of the meeting date. The minutes shall be deemed approved by the members unless any objection or claim is made within fifteen (15) days of receipt.

Article 11 — National Coordinator of E-RIHS (COUNTRY)

11.1 The National Coordinator is appointed for a term of three (3) years, renewable once, by a decision of the Steering Committee taken by a two-thirds majority of the votes cast. If necessary, the National Coordinator may propose a Deputy National Coordinator to the Steering Committee. If applicable, the Deputy National Coordinator is appointed by a decision of the Steering Committee.

11.2 The National Coordinator:

- implements the decisions of the Steering Committee;

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

- implements the Activities resulting from the involvement of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) in E-RIHS Europe;
- organises, with the assistance of the host institution, the activities of E-RIHS (COUNTRY);
- represents E-RIHS (COUNTRY) in the National Nodes Committee of E-RIHS Europe and also liaises with the Director-General of E-RIHS Europe;
- prepares the service agreement between E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and E-RIHS Europe (hereinafter referred to as the "Service Level Agreement"), which consolidates all national contributions to E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and E-RIHS Europe;
- makes any proposals to the Steering Committee regarding the Activities to be implemented each year;
- prepares the annual report on the Activities implemented each year for submission to the Steering Committee for approval.

Article 12 — Scientific Council

12.1 Mission

The Scientific Council reviews the research orientations of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and their implementation. It also has an advisory role regarding the inclusion or exclusion of instruments offered by service providers listed in Appendix II.

12.2 Composition

The Scientific Council is composed of a maximum of six (6) experts external to the service providers, representative of the scientific activities of E-RIHS (COUNTRY), appointed by the Steering Committee upon the proposal of the National Coordinator.

12.3 Operation

The meetings of the Scientific Council are chaired by one of its members, elected from among them by a simple majority, for a five-year term, renewable once.

The Scientific Council meets at least once (1) per year at the initiative of its chair. The chair decides on the appropriate communication methods.

The chair reports to the Steering Committee and the National Coordinator.

The National Coordinator attends the meetings of the Scientific Council.

The National Coordinator shall take all necessary measures to ensure that the members of the Scientific Council respect the confidentiality of the information they become aware of in the course of their activities within the Council, particularly by signing a confidentiality agreement. This confidentiality agreement is established between the individual and the host institution, which is mandated by the other Parties for this purpose.

Article 13 — General Assembly of Service Providers

13.1 Mission

The General Assembly of Service Providers represents all scientific teams from laboratories involved in E-RIHS (COUNTRY). Its role is to:

- a) liaise with user communities and communicate their suggestions and needs concerning the access offered by E-RIHS and E-RIHS (COUNTRY);
- b) facilitate exchanges between service providers on best practices for infrastructure cost evaluation;
- c) develop initial and ongoing training offerings that align with the needs of the various stakeholders in heritage science;
- d) establish solutions for data interoperability from E-RIHS (COUNTRY) activities by applying the principles of open science;
- e) organise communication and dissemination activities to promote the results of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and heritage sciences in general;
- f) propose any action to the Steering Committee that it deems necessary to better fulfil the missions of E-RIHS (COUNTRY).

13.2 Composition

The General Assembly of Service Providers is composed of one representative per service provider listed in Appendix I of the Agreement. Each representative may be accompanied by a maximum of two experts.

The National Coordinator is an ex officio member and may also invite additional experts.

The composition of the General Assembly of Service Providers is communicated to the Steering Committee by the National Coordinator.

13.3 Operation

13.3.1 The meetings of the General Assembly of Service Providers are chaired by the National Coordinator.

13.3.2 The General Assembly of Service Providers meets at least once (1) per year at the initiative of its chair. The chair decides on the appropriate communication methods.

13.3.3 The General Assembly may also create thematic groups on its own initiative, which meet in additional sessions and elect their leader by a simple majority of the representatives wishing to participate in the group during a plenary meeting.

13.3.4 The meetings of the General Assembly are documented in minutes prepared under the responsibility of the National Coordinator. The minutes are sent to each member of the General Assembly of Service Providers within fifteen (15) days following the meeting. They are considered accepted by the members if no objection or claim has been made within fifteen (15) days of their receipt.

Article 14 — Leading Institution

14.1 The Parties acknowledge the (INSTITUTION) as the leading institution of E-RIHS (COUNTRY). They emphasise the importance of the proper coordination between the governance structure of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and that of the leading institution.

14.2 The leading institution undertakes to:

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

- a) facilitate the implementation of the Activities of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and assist the National Coordinator in fulfilling their mission;
- b) Coordinate the national cash contribution to E-RIHS Europe;
- c) promote E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and its Activities among its members and encourage synergy between its various activities.

Article 15 — Relations with the European E-RIHS Infrastructure

The Parties agree that E-RIHS (COUNTRY) will be represented in E-RIHS Europe at two levels:

- within the National Nodes Committee of E-RIHS Europe by the National Coordinator of E-RIHS (COUNTRY);
- in the General Assembly of E-RIHS Europe by (GA Representatives).

Article 16 — Confidentiality

16.1 The Parties agree to maintain the confidentiality of information exchanged in the context of the performance of this Agreement. No Party shall disclose to any third party, without the prior written consent of the other Parties, any information classified as confidential and communicated in the framework of E-RIHS (COUNTRY).

16.2 The confidentiality obligations shall apply to all representatives of the Parties, members of the committees and bodies of E-RIHS (COUNTRY), as well as any other person invited to or participating in meetings. These obligations shall remain in force for a period of five (5) years following the termination of a Party's participation in the Agreement.

16.3 Each Party undertakes to take all necessary measures to ensure that its representatives and agents comply with this obligation of confidentiality.

Article 17 — Intellectual Property

17.1 This Agreement shall in no way affect the intellectual property rights owned by the Parties or their representatives prior to the entry into force of the Agreement.

17.2 The intellectual property rights arising from Activities carried out within the framework of this Agreement shall be shared in proportion to the respective contributions of the Parties, and in compliance with applicable intellectual property laws.

17.3 The Parties agree to inform each other of any creation or innovation resulting from work undertaken within the framework of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and undertake to negotiate in good faith the terms of sharing the related rights.

Article 18 — Amendments to the Agreement

18.1 Any amendment to this Agreement must be approved by the Steering Committee by a two-thirds majority of the members present or represented.

18.2 Amendments so adopted shall take effect upon signature of an addendum by all the Parties.

Article 19 — Dispute Resolution

19.1 In the event of any dispute or disagreement regarding the interpretation or performance of this Agreement, the Parties shall endeavour to reach an amicable solution through the Steering Committee.

19.2 If no amicable agreement is reached within six (6) months from the date of the dispute, the matter shall be referred to the competent courts.

Article 20 — Duration and Termination of the Agreement

20.1 This Agreement is concluded for an indefinite period.

20.2 Any Party may terminate its participation in the Agreement in accordance with the conditions set out in Article 8. The withdrawal shall not release the Party from obligations undertaken prior to the date of termination.

20.3 The Agreement may be terminated by mutual consent of all the Parties or by judicial decision in the event of a serious breach by a Party of its contractual obligations.

Article 21 — Confidentiality and Publications

21.1 Confidentiality

Except with the written agreement of the Party from whom it received such information, each Party undertakes to keep confidential and not disclose any information, including results and prior knowledge communicated to it by said Party as confidential (hereinafter referred to as the "Confidential Information"), to any third party or to anyone other than those of its employees who need to know such information for the purposes of executing the Activities or fulfilling the Agreement. Each Party further agrees not to use the Confidential Information for any purpose other than performing the tasks entrusted to it under the Agreement and in fulfillment of its obligations under the Agreement.

Each Party shall take all necessary measures to preserve the confidential nature of the Confidential Information it receives and shall treat such information with the same level of protection as it employs to protect and safeguard its own Confidential Information against any disclosure to a third party, this level of protection being no less than a strict duty of care. Each Party shall limit the disclosure of the Confidential Information solely to its employees and/or persons involved in the Activities.

Each Party will inform the said individuals of the obligations of the Agreement and shall vouch for their compliance with the non-disclosure obligations concerning the Confidential Information to third parties.

However, the above provisions do not apply to Confidential Information for which the receiving Party can provide written evidence that:

- it was already in its possession at the time of communication;
- it was in the public domain at the time of communication or subsequently entered the public domain through no fault or negligence of its own;
- it was provided by a third party with no obligation of confidentiality attached.

D2.4 Best Practices and Lessons Learned for Establishing E-RIHS National Node

The confidentiality undertaking, the subject of this article, remains in force throughout the duration of the Agreement and for a period of five (5) years following its expiration or termination.

21.2 Publications — Communications

21.2.1 Any proposed publication or communication regarding research results achieved as part of the Activities must comply with the current E-RIHS publication policy. Publications and communications must acknowledge E-RIHS and the contributions of each Party, as well as the access providers associated with the Activities. A mandatory statement must be included in the "Acknowledgements" section, as follows: "The authors acknowledge financial support from the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) for the XXX experiments conducted on the YYY platform" (where XXX denotes the type of instrument used, and YYY represents the relevant access provider(s)).

This mandatory statement may be adapted upon a decision made by the National Coordinators within the framework of E-RIHS Europe.

21.2.2 However, the provisions of Article 21.2.1 above shall not prevent:

- the obligation on individuals involved in the Activities to submit an annual activity report to their governing institution, provided that such communication does not constitute a disclosure under business law or privacy protection laws;
- the presentation of theses by researchers whose scientific work relates to the Activities.

CHAPTER 4 — Final Provisions

Article 22 — Working Language

The Parties acknowledge the importance of using (NATIONAL LANGUAGE) within the field of heritage science generally and specifically within the activities of E-RIHS (COUNTRY). However, they allow the use of English in communications and commitments between E-RIHS (COUNTRY) and E-RIHS Europe.

Article 23 — Activity Report

The Parties agree on the necessity of making the activities of E-RIHS (COUNTRY) public through an annual activity report.

Article 24 — Amendment to the Agreement

Any amendment to any provision of this Agreement shall only take effect following a written agreement in the form of an addendum to the Agreement, duly signed by all Parties.

Article 25 — Duration and Scope of Validity of the Agreement

This Agreement is adopted by the Parties for a period of six (6) years from the date of its signature and may be renewed annually upon expiry by a simple addendum.

Article 26 — Dispute Resolution — Applicable Law

In the event of any difficulties arising between the Parties regarding the interpretation or execution of the Agreement, the Parties shall consult with the aim of reaching an amicable solution. To this end, any disagreement shall be notified in writing to the Steering Committee by the most diligent of the concerned Parties. The Steering Committee shall convene within fifteen (15) days of notification to attempt to resolve the dispute. If no resolution is reached within forty-five (45) days of notification, the matter shall be referred to the respective leadership of the concerned Parties. If a disagreement persists, the competent courts shall be engaged.

This Agreement is governed by national law.